

One Day National Level Seminar
on

ROLE OF DIGITAL BANKING IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Editor
Prof. Rudrakumar M.M.

Organized By
Department of Commerce (UG & PG)
Nehru Memorial College, Kurunjibag, Sullia. Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka-574327

(Re-accredited with 'B+' Grade by NAAC)
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E-BANKING: A NEW TREND IN DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The present era of industrialisation and globalisation has added a lot of comforts and luxuries to human life. Through this banking also become a so easier task. Electronic banking is a new trend in modern banking era which allows it's user to perform banking transactions without visiting to the bank as well as without usage of any physical currency. This research paper is based on the modern changes in the banking system especially in Dakshina Kannada District. But the awareness and the operating knowledge is very much needed for the public of Dakshina Kannada District rural people.

Keywords: E-Banking, Modernisation, Demonetisation, UPI, Mobile.

Introduction:

The present era of industrialisation and globalisation has added a lot of comforts and luxuries to human life. Through this banking also become a so easier task. The banking sector has very low impact on the environment. By the introduction IT enabled services in form of internet banking, mobile banking etc. banking sector has reduced the dependency on paper money simultaneously the customer's visit to the banks also reduced. More importantly after the Demonetisation made by Government of India e-banking is becoming more popular

Electronic Banking:

The Electronic banking is one of the most progressive banking policies nowadays especially in this modern era of digitalization. As the name tells, Electronic

banking is a new trend in modern banking era which allows it's user to perform banking transactions without visiting to the bank as well as without usage of any physical currency. Now a day's strategy, policies, and implementation regarding information technology have become the foremost concern to all banks since it has a direct impact on the management decisions, plans, and products and services to be offered by Banks. At present Banks, all over the world are concentrating more on their e-banking activities, and are expanding their electronic banking activities through the use of wireless networks and venturing into some new areas of electronic commerce globally.

Advantages of Electronic Banking:

1. It will be very convenient to all customers if cashless banking is implemented. No risk of carrying cash in pockets and bags
2. Anyone can easily access their account history at any time
3. Any c Electronic banking transactions are legally visible/ traceable. so the people cannot hide their income level
4. Tax payable will be increases as the customer get easy access to his expenses may be increases.

Electronic Banking Products:

As the banks of Dakshina Kannada Distrcit are slowly moving towards Electronic banking, various products are helping those banks to make it successful. They are as follows:

- 1) Bank Cards
- 2) NEFT
- 3) RTGS
- 4) USSD
- 5) AEPS
- 6) UPI
- 7) Mobile Wallets
- 8) Online banking
- 9) Mobile Apps

❖ Bank Cards:

For encouraging cashless society banks are issuing various plastic cards like Debit Cards, Credit Cards etc. so that the customers need not to carry cash with them.

❖ **NEFT & RTGS (National Electronic Fund Transfer, Real Time Gross Settlement):**

Both these facilities allow the customer to transfer any amount of fund to anywhere in India easily.

❖ **USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data):**

This is a protocol used by GSM cellular telephones to communicate with the service provider computer. This feature allows WAP browsing, prepaid call back services, mobile money services etc.

❖ **AEPS (Adhaar Enables Payment System):**

Nowadays banks are allowing Adhaar Cards as customers KYC document. From this adhaar linked bank account holders can use the funds through their Adhaar number.

❖ **UPI (Unified Payment Interface):**

Bank accounts can be linked to the customer's smart phones so that he can access his account through his smart phones no need to visit bank premise.

❖ **Mobile wallets:**

Various software companies are providing their own mobile wallet applications to allow the customer to get the benefits of UPI based features. Various mobile wallets are oxygen wallet, mobikwick etc.

❖ **Online banking:**

Not only by using smart phones but any other internet connected tablets, PCs etc can also be used to perform banking transactions through online banking feature.

❖ **Mobile apps**

Unless UPI and also Mobile Wallets each and every banks are creating their own applications to be connected with their customers and also to provide more services to them.

Objectives of the study:

This paper has been prepared with the following objectives:

- To understand the concept of Electronic banking
- To grasp the various products under Electronic banking
- To analyse the methods, how the banks are popularising Electronic banking in Dakshina Kannada district
- To identify the problems faced by the banks and the customers in Electronic banking
- To make the solutions to banks as well as customer for implementing Electronic banking

Research Methodology:

This data is personally collected by a structured questionnaire method to the bank customers of Dakshina Kannada district. According to the convenience sampling method was used to get the proforma filled. The researcher could do the analysis of 200 for customers and 53 proformas for Bankers.

Data Interpretation and Analysis:

Table 1: Awareness about Electronic Banking

Products	Aware	Not Aware
Bank Cards	81%	19%
NEFT&RTGS	78%	22%
USSD	70%	30%
AEPS	55%	45%
UPI	50%	50%
Mobile Wallet	70%	30%
Online Banking	75%	25%
Mobile Apps	63%	37%

Source: Primary data

From table 1, we can easily understand that, in Dakshina Kannada district awareness about electronic banking products are comparatively high. A small percentage of urban area people are to be educated.

Table 2: Users of electronic banking Products

Products	User	Not User
Bank Cards	98%	02%
NEFT&RTGS	70%	30%
USSD	55%	45%
AEPS	45%	55%
UPI	30%	70%
Mobile Wallet	60%	40%
Online Banking	60%	40%
Mobile Apps	70%	30%

Source: Primary data

From the table 2, shows the products like Bank cards, NEFT and RTGS etc. are highly used by the people in Dakshina Kannada district. In upcoming days we can hope for the better usage of other products also.

Table 3: Perceptions towards electronic banking

Products	Highly satisfied	Satisfied	Not Satisfied
Bank Cards	40%	50%	10%
NEFT&RTGS	20%	30%	50%
USSD	30%	30%	40%
AEPS	18%	22%	60%
UPI	20%	25%	55%
Mobile Wallet	40%	30%	30%
Online Banking	50%	25%	25%
Mobile Apps	50%	30%	20%

Source: Primary data

From the table 3, shows the perception of general public towards electronic banking products. Majority number of customers among its users are highly satisfied with these products

Table 4: The Effect of Digital India Initiative on E-Banking Given in Table

Nature	Customer (200)		Bankers (53)	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Very high	35	17.5	07	13.21
High	50	25	22	41.51
Moderate	106	53	21	39.62
Low	05	2.5	02	3.77
Very low	01	0.5	00	0.00
No effective at all	01	0.5	00	0.00
Cannot say anything	02	01	01	1.89
Total	200	100.0	53	100.0

Source: Primary Data
 $X^2=6.477$ $p<0.001$ vhs

Interpretation:

With many problems, we found that the digital India initiative on e-banking in Dakshina Kannada is moderate according to 53% of the customers and 21% of the Bankers. But 22% of the bankers say the effect is high. But it's not so with the customers. Because only 25% of customers said that the effect is increased in Dakshina Kannada. But the percentage of people who say the impact is low is only 0.5% in customers and 0.00% among bankers. The comparison between these two groups is found to be significant($p < 0.001$).

Limitations of Study:

Every study has some type of limitations in any aspect. Regarding to this, following limitations are mentioned

- The sample size is not so large to generalise it
- Time frame was the biggest limitation
- It could not be believe that all the respondents have given or accurate data
- This study and the data collection is made on limited sources

Findings:

- Internet facility is not very much developed in the Dakshina Kannada Rural. Therefore it is a challenging task for them to promote electronic banking.
- Even the literates of this place will also have the fear of safety and security of their funds
- Basic infrastructure facility is not well developed in this area
- Immediate transformation of traditional banking to electronic banking is very difficult task. People also may not adjust to this system immediately.
- Compare to traditional system, service charges will be very high.

Suggestions:

Compare to Government sector banks, private sector banks are providing more opportunities for cashless society. The recent events like demonetisation also side by side helping to making electronic banking. The following are my suggestions to banks regarding my topic

- There must be safe and secure cyber security in every e-banking payment system
- The bank should promote good infrastructure facility to its customers to use electronic banking products
- The service charges on digital payments should be reduced or banned.
- The bank should provide various offers like discounts, cashback etc to encourage customers

➤ All retailers should have digital swipe machine or other digital payment option.

Conclusion:

"E-Banking: A new trend in Dakshina Kannada District". It is a research paper based on the researches and the modern changes in the banking system especially in Dakshina Kannada District. But the awareness and the operating knowledge is very much needed for the public of Dakshina Kannada District. If the banks should think on this, it will be very easier and Dakshina Kannada District can be called as the Largest E-Banking service provider of Karnataka state.

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